

A DEONTOLOGICAL CRITIQUE OF YOUTHS ATTITUDE TOWARDS PROSTITUTION

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Abstract: *The attitude towards prostitution in the contemporary society has called for a thorough reflection. The act of prostitution is no longer seen as evil, rather, a normal way of life or a means of acquiring more wealth in this economic imbalance and difficulties. However, the research has it that prostitution did not originate today, the origin of prostitution can be traced back to the ancient era and even to the biblical scriptures. But these are not a norm stand to justify prostitution especially amongst the underage children. The research argues that prostitution violates the fundamental moral principles such as respect for autonomy, non-maleficence and human dignity. The research employed a phenomenological method of data collection whereby the ethical implications of youth attitude towards prostitution was exposed. The findings of the work contribute to the understanding of bigger issues surrounding the study of prostitution and informed strategies for promoting ethical awareness, and responsible behaviours among the youths.*

Introduction

The society has decayed with several acts of immorality which affects every member of the society directly or indirectly. One of the ugly incidents that is proliferating in our society today is prostitution. The act of prostitution is no longer seen as evil, rather, a normal way of life or a means of acquiring more wealth in this economic imbalance and difficulties. The most worrisome situation is that this job is not just done by the adults but rather, it has been taken

over by the kids of about 12 to 15 years of age. These children belong to what is now termed “Gen Z” generation. This generation is popularized with impunity and immorality. They have lost sense of morality and refused to learn from the footprint of their parents and grandparents. They thought that everything is used to acquire more wealth irrespective of the means at which such wealth is acquired. This article was prompted from the recent video clip released of some young Nigerian girls who

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were caught in Accra (Ghana) and confessed that they were brought to Ghana for sex pay work (Prostitution). The age differences of those girls were between 15 to 17 years. After watching the video clip, I went to my enclave, meditated reflected on what we really wish for the future generation. Many will way that I sound how I am currently sounding because I am a Catholic priest, No, I am bothered because we don't know what we are doing to ourselves. How can children of such age be forced to face such life at such young age by their own brother? We gathered in the video clip through one of the girls that the children were taken from Nigeria to Ghana by their own brother. It was confessed in the video that one of the under aged girls was a direct sister to the named boy and they hail from Abia State. Nevertheless, a friend of mine told me how they released some Nigerian girls who went into prostitution and were caught and thrown in prison at Cyprus. We learnt that the girls had stayed for over six months before their video clip came online through a Nigerian in Cyprus. Though, effort has been made to release the girls, what about others in different places yet to be identified?

What happened to internal prostitutes who are patronized by most of us here? At the course of this research, I went to most of the Hotels and club centres in Abakaliki. I disguised myself and visited as a guest to some renowned and known

Hotels like Tycoon Hotel, Monablis Hotel, New Haven Hotel and Cyrene Hotel. What I gathered as priest was a shame on humanity. I discovered that the age range of Gen Z prostitutes is within 13-17 years. They are people beyond such, no doubt. As that was not enough, I decided to visit some club centres like Citi Hub and Doxology refreshment club centres. At the club centres, it is discovered that the clubbers are the young school children who are either between first year and final year or a young school leaver who is making effort to start a life. Also, there are adults that equally engaged in prostitution. I went to Hausa quarters and discovered a brothel with a tattered building where men risk their life in the service of prostitutes with cheaper rates. During my interrogation with some of them, I came to realize the reason why some of them ventured into the business of prostitution, how they collect per night and the risk of prostitution. My greatest challenge in this research is the discovery of the fact that most of the people sleeping with these children are adults and learned men like us.

However, one may stand to say that prostitution did not originate today, the origin of prostitution can be traced back to the ancient and even to the biblical scriptures. But these are not a norm stand to justify prostitution especially amongst the underage children. So, in this work we shall be making analysis of prostitution from its

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concept, history, reasons and then deontological critique.

The level of impunity and lackadaisical attitude of this generation has called for a serious check to avert what could be termed as 'immoral generation'. It will be a thing of shame that no one speaks against prostitution and other immoral attitudes of this generation. The prostitutes have devised their mode of communication, association and relationship.

The growing nature of prostitutes in the society today is on a serious rampage. With the appearance of trafficking networks and, moreover, with the development of new technology, the traditional image of prostitution has greatly evolved. The locations of prostitution have multiplied. In addition to street prostitution, a hidden prostitution has sprung up in massage parlors, at bars, in brothels (legal or not, depending on the country), dating services, and above all, on the internet. Due to internet, nothing is easier than publishing an advertisement or nude photos, and selling one's body for money with the most discretion and anonymity. Today, there is a growing number of young women, sometimes very young, but also men, who use these means to make ends meet. In a society where sex is displayed everywhere (advertisements, television), prostitution appears more and more often to be a possible solution to a difficult situation and many people

no longer hesitate to take this leap, "just to get by." How many are there? We don't know. We are only beginning to identify them. They are students who struggle to pay for their studies, the unemployed and the employed at the end of a difficult month, or even women who have a regular and sometimes well-paid job. They are men, more and more numerous, who sell their bodies to other men but, recently, also to women who are claiming their "right" to paid services. So, we shall discuss in detail the concepts and theories involved in prostitution.

Conceptual Clarification

The word prostitution is derived from the Latin word "prostituta" meaning pro (up-front) and situere (offer for sale) (Alobo, 2014). It means up-front sale or service for money. The Wikipedia online Dictionary defined prostitution as the act or acts and practice of promiscuous sexual relationship, especially for money (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wik>). Further, it describes the state of being prosecuted as debasement. Prostitution is an act of indulging in sexual activity in exchange of monetary reward. All these definitions justify the fact that prostitution itself is voluntary and it is only for financial rewards. People prefer using the term "sex worker" instead of the term "prostitute" because the former sounds less offensive. According to May, Harocopos and Hough (2000), the term 'sex worker' refers to those

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engaged in prostitution. They posit that the term has been adopted as it's free of complicated, derogatory, and sexist connotations which are more commonly associated with the term 'prostitute'. It is clear from the definitions reviewed that prostitution is a transaction between two parties: the one offering his/her body, and the person patronising the service. In the market situation, the buyer transacts with the seller, at the hospital, the patient interacts with the doctor, in the school, we have the teacher and the student but in the case of prostitution, while there are two parties engaged in the sex transaction, the buyer is overlooked since the term prostitute refers to only the one offering the service. There is no equivalent term for the one buying the services of the prostitute. Shaver (1988) also asserts that when looking at prostitution historically, it becomes clear that those punished for the crime are the providers of sex. Western society and most sex worker activists prefer the term "sex worker" instead of the term "prostitute".

Harcourt and Donovan compiled a long list of the different types of sexual services practiced by sex workers around the world⁵. From this list, they grouped types of sexual services into two categories: direct and indirect sex work. Direct sex work refers to services, such as indoor and outdoor prostitution as well as escort services. This type of sex work typically involves the

exchange of sex for a fee in which genital contact is common. Indirect sex work refers to services, such as lap dancing, stripping, and virtual sex services (over the Internet or phone). Genital contact is less common in this type of sex work; however, a fee is still exchanged for the service. As posited by Taylor and Jamieson (1993), people engage in sexual activity for pleasure but others engage in it for economic reasons. Thus, the sex industry works as the principles of demand and supply in the business world. There has been consistent demand for sex over the years, which has culminated in more people, especially women offering sex for economic gains. Therefore, if this increment is consistent, it stands to prove the reason for the increment in the number of sex workers who are engaged in prostitution. According to Cusick et al. (2009), calculating the number of commercial sex workers is very difficult as sex work is mostly hidden and the population is transient, with people moving in and out of sex work constantly. The sex-work industry is made up of both men and women. However, women make up the majority of the workers. Women make up the majority of the sex work population, with some estimates suggesting the proportion is around 85-90 percent (Scambler, 2008). Another study by Wilcox and Christmann (2006) on male sex workers in the Yorkshire area of Kirklees found a small number of male sex workers working in the

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area. This stands to reason that though men are engaged in prostitution, women prostitutes constitute the larger portion. The patronisers of the sex industry involve both the learned and the unlearned. It is therefore difficult to categorise prostitutes as possessing little education. Thus, Roberts et al. (2010) assert that some students engage in sex work to help fund their studies and that the numbers are thought to have increased with the introduction of top-up tuition fees.

In the temple of the goddess of love, priestesses in exchange for donations for the goddess would offer up their bodies (Doufor, 1902). Once a year in the Mylitty temple in ancient Babylon, each woman had to give herself to a foreigner, who would pay, in order to fulfill their sacred duty (Sanyer, 2015). In ancient Greece, the first brothels (lupanarium) were created in Athens by Solon in the sixth century BC. Prostitution was public and legal in ancient Rome (Sanyer, 2015). A special office was established in 260 BC, which was coordinated by an aedile. Aediles were responsible for guarding the peace in the lupanarium and controlling the taxes of income from prostitutes (Sanyer, 2015).

Prostitution life was a concern in many public places. In the Roman baths, for example, special cabins existed, where erotic massages and oral and classic sex were performed by both female and male prostitutes (Sanyer, 2015). Prostitution practices from ancient Rome were uncovered on

a fresco from Pompeii. Prostitution was common in many large cities during the middle Ages. Professional prostitutes wore red bows on their arms as a sign of pride of guild membership, with the income from brothels feeding the municipal treasury. In the middle ages, the first similarity to red light districts was established, with the names of the streets referred to erotic or sex services (e.g., Pousse-Penil or Puits d'amour).

In the sixteenth century, there was an attitudes against prostitution. Syphilis transmitted to Europe from Columbian expeditions to America could have contributed to this (Harper, 2008). Practicing this profession became a crime, a transgression against human and divine laws. Together with this new type of crime, new ways of administering the penalty were created. Published by Charles V in 1530, Norms and the Police Reform severely prohibited prostitution with the penalties contained in them being extremely cruel. The eighteenth century was "The Golden Age of Prostitution," and during this period, prostitution was widely popular. There were numerous places in Paris and London where prostitutes could receive training in order to be professional and adaptable (Robert, 1992). Prostitution began to develop in the USA at the beginning of the nineteenth century, where bawdy houses were tolerated in American cities (D'emillo, 1988). New Orleans is viewed by historians as the largest city brothel of all time.

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Various systems of regulating prostitutes and monitoring brothels were developed in Europe (Head, 2017). Many prostitutes sexually served soldiers of both sides during World War I and World War II. Many soldiers were exposed to venereal diseases through these interpersonal contacts. In the Japanese war brothels, 200,000 women from China and Korea, called “comfort women,” were forced into prostitution (Head, 2017). Sex tourism, defined as travelling for sexual intercourse, emerged as a controversial aspect of Western tourism and globalization in the late twentieth century.

However, the novel book, *Beyond the Horizon* by Amma Darko presented the nature of prostitution among African women. Amma Darko in her novel *Beyond the Horizon* presents to the reader a young naïve girl in the village, Mara, who is married by a young man and taken to the city. In the city, she goes through a lot of hustle and humiliation from her husband in the corrugated iron sheet structure they call home. Her husband moves to Europe to find greener pastures with many promises to Mara, the main character in the work under study. Akobi, Mara’s husband later makes arrangements for the wife to join him in Europe which she obliges, only to come to the realization upon relocation to Europe that, her husband has deceived her into prostitution. And more shockingly, Mara finds out that the proceeds of her sex work are used for

funding the luxurious stay of her husband’s concubine in the European country, Germany. Mara, now a free prostitute, sends a letter to Akobi’s newfound European wife, Gitte who had given so much money to Akobi to build a house for them to relocate to Africa. After the receipt of the letter, Akobi is sent to prison while his African woman lover, Comfort is deported.

The work presents the readers with a deep insight into the practice of prostitution among African women in the diaspora. Through the texts, we have identified certain issues that push women into the practice of prostitution. We find patriarchy as a prominent factor that pushes women into prostitution. In Nigeria, and even after migration to Europe, women who usually go into prostitution, depend wholly on men who bring them for shelter, food, and other necessities of life. This affords the men the opportunity to initiate them into the sex trade. This practice of patriarchy is further substantiated, when Vivian asserts to validate the reality of the dependence of the African women on their invitees in Europe, thus:

I came here full of hope and found here too, I have to continue depending wholly on Osey. He makes every arrangement and simply gives me orders. Even the money I make, he controls it. I can't buy anything without his consent, not even for my mother at home (Darko, 1995).

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Vivian is not alone in this dependence on the men, Mara upon arrival in Europe, depends wholly on Akobi, who is known in Germany as Cobby. Akobi decides what Mara eats, where she goes and even the work she does and this proves very instrumental in his plan to push her into the sex trade. Kaye also expresses her total dependence on her then-boyfriend after she arrives in Germany. From the presentation of these three characters cited, Amma Darko exposes the reader to the patriarchal situation that the African woman migrant encounters, where everything she does is dependent on the man who brings her abroad. This situation usually puts the man in a better position to push the dependent woman into prostitution. Amma Darko presents the reader with yet another stunning revelation of how African maidens get initiated into this trade that attracts so much displeasure on African soil. The men who initiate the women blackmail, and command them to engage in sex work. Afterward, some of the men threaten the women to blackmail them by sending images of the women to their (women's) families in Africa if they (the women) decide to quit the prostitution they were initiated into. In the text, Akobi can push Mara into prostitution by playing a recorded video that contains her (Mara) in a sex orgy with many men and threatens her that if she does not engage in

prostitution, he (Akobi) will send the video to her family in Ghana.

The situation was this: the three of us were watching a video film that showed me completely naked, with men's hands moving all over my body. Then some held my two legs wide apart while one after the other, men, many men, white, black, brown, and even one who looked Chinese, took turns upon me. All this was captured clearly in the video film. And this was what Osey and Akobi blackmailed me with so that I agreed to do the job at Peepy (Darko, 1995).

Kaye also narrates her experience at the time her then-boyfriend brings her to Europe, coerced her into prostitution and pocketed every mark she made, and kept her in the sex trade by blackmailing her with pictures he had taken of her in action with different men "You back out today, tomorrow these pictures will be on their way back to your family at home" (Darko, 1995). The analysis of the practice of prostitution in the text discloses the nature of the characterisation presented by Amma Darko. Different characters present the reader with different ways of the practice of prostitution. Mara, the main character in the text, begins her practice of prostitution as a naïve recruit who has been blackmailed and coerced into prostitution. After she was coerced into the sex trade, the man who ushers her into it decides with the pimp to send every mark (amount) she makes into his (the

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man's) account. The woman does not get any amount of money that comes from the use of her own body in the sex trade. Akobi takes all the money that Mara earns, as she asserts: "But the money I made laying with men at Peepy, I saw none of it.... Every day, apart from Sundays, I took on at least three men. What they paid me went to Akobi" (Darko, 1995).

It is identified that certain traits in Mara are very instrumental in Akobi's ability to initiate her into the sex trade. Mara is very faithful to her husband to the extent that at certain times she takes his orders to be divine. When he outlines his travel plans to her, Mara asserts that even if Akobi had asked her to offer her head she would have done it without questioning. Mara's naivety also accounts for her easy initiation into the sex business. She is so "green" to the extent that Vivian even finds it difficult to alert her on certain issues associated with her stay and work in Europe. Mara starts work at Peepy with other prostitutes who by obligation have to paint their lips and their cheeks with a red-like colour each. This paint is supposed to be more of a trademark for the profession – prostitution – than a mere make-up. Thus, Mara asserts:

I shiver at the sight of my sore cracked lips which still show through the multiple layers of the glossy crimson paint I apply to hide them. This gaudy pink rouge I've plastered on my ebony black face looks horrid too, I know, but I wear it

because it's a trademark of my profession (Darko, 1995).

Mara now comes to her senses in the sex trade and stops working for Akobi by leaving Peepy for another brothel, where the money she earns will come to her directly. Amma Darko uses Mara's character to express resilience, in the face of oppression. Vivian is another character the author uses to portray the practice of prostitution in the diaspora and who, being in a similar situation to that of Mara, also works as a prostitute and she has no control over the proceed since it goes to her boyfriend, Osey. Vivian cannot even use any part of the money to buy something for herself. Vivian expresses: "Even the money I make, he controls it" (Darko, 1995). After her initiation, the money Vivian makes goes to her fiancé, Osey. Darko uses Vivian's character to show submission to authority and the possibility of a woman taking her life into her hands, later in the work. Kaye is also a character that Darko uses to disclose some knowledge about the rationale behind the African woman's practice of prostitution in the diaspora.

Types of Prostitution

In the society today, they are different types of prostitutions which include the following. Street: Clients are being approached on the street, in parks, and in other public places. Serviced on side streets, in vehicles, or in short-term

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accommodations. The prostitute solicits customers while waiting at street corners or walking alongside a street, usually dressed in revealing, suggestive clothing. To distinguish themselves from other sex workers, the prostitute (commonly referred to as a "hooker," "street hooker," or "street walker") appears to be minding his or her own business and waits for the customers to initiate contact. Call girls, escort agencies, and workers in bars, brothels, and massage parlors are all examples of "indoor prostitution," which includes call girls, escort agencies, and workers in bars, brothels, and massage parlors. Indoor prostitution is generally safer for the workers because it has little or no negative impact on the surrounding community, it pays well, and the workers are more satisfied with their work than street prostitutes (Weitzer, 2000).

Brothel: Sites that are solely dedicated to the provision of sex. Security is superior to that of the street. Authorities frequently issue licenses.

Escort: The client makes contact with the sex worker over the phone or through hotel staff. The shadiest type of sex work. Because of the low client turnover, it is relatively expensive. The service is provided at the client's residence or in their hotel room. Escort agencies keep a database of employees of various types in order to serve a larger clientele. Some organizations may specialize in a specific type of prostitution. Male-

to-male, female-to-male, and female-to-female escort agencies exist, as well as a few male-to-female escort agencies. Typically, agencies specialize in only one sex. Some escort agencies have trans-sexual prostitutes available.

Private: The client calls the sex worker. Similar to escorts, but services are provided on the premises of the sex worker. 'Flat' prostitution high cost services in rented, serviced inner-city units is a variant in London and other major cities.

Window or doorway: Brothels with sex workers on display in public places. In cold climates, windows are preferred, while in warmer climates, doorways are preferred.

Club, pub bar, karaoke bar, dance hall: Clients who are met at alcohol vending machines and served on-site or elsewhere.

Other all-male venues: Men-only establishments such as barbershops, bathhouses, saunas, and mining camps were used to recruit clients. Onsite or off-site maintenance is available.

Transport (ship, truck, train): Sex workers may board vehicles to provide service to the crew or passengers, as well as pick up clients from stations and terminals.

Sex tourism: Some sex tourism group form around a number of websites where they brag about their conquests, share photos of their sex partners, and discuss how to find prostitution at

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the best possible price in foreign countries while avoiding detection both at home and abroad.

Other methods of solicitation: Through a variety of media, such as noticeboard and newspaper advertisements, 'sex worker catalogues' with phone numbers, the internet via virtual brothels, and so on. The majority of services are provided in brothels and other indoor locations.

The Challenges of Prostitution

Prostitution is the practice of engaging in relatively indiscriminate sexual activity, in general with someone who is not a spouse or a friend, in exchange for immediate payment of money or other valuables. Prostitutes may be female or male or transgender, and prostitution may entail heterosexual or homosexual activity, but historically most prostitutes have been women, and most clients are men. Prostitution has become rampant in Nigeria today among teenagers and adults. Studies of prostitution have focused largely on individuals involved in the commercial sex trade, with an emphasis on understanding the public health effect of this behavior. However, a broader understanding of how prostitution affects mental and physical health is needed.

The sex workers has their reasons for indulging in such business. Most at times, the major aim of prostitution will be to survive the economic challenges in our society. According to Kingsley (1971) poverty triggered the rapid spread of

prostitution in urban areas. It provides those involved a considerable amount of income to support their families as well as supply a steady flow of remittances from urban to rural areas or from prostitutes working overseas. Lamptey (2000) asserted that family expectations and problems are common factors why many people enter into the prostitution business. Women in particular are pressured to pay for their children's education or support a sick family member. Poverty and economic hardship largely predispose women and girls into sex work. The root cause of prostitution seems to be poverty since these women and girls see prostitution as a way of supplementing their low income. More so, Adebajo (2012) in his study in Agbor, interviewed prostitutes and he discovered that the high rate of poverty is the pushing force behind the increasing rate of prostitution.

Similarly, unemployment has been viewed to be the reason behind the high rate of crime in urban areas. Obviously, those who are gainfully employed do not engage in prostitution. Adebisi (2012) observed that some girls engage in prostitution after graduating from high institutions and failing to secure gainful employment having roamed the streets for jobs without success and no capital to start any business rather give into men's sexual advances in exchange for money to keep body and soul together. The high rate of unemployment has

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lured some youths especially women to turn to prostitution so as to make a living for themselves and families. Unemployment is one of the critical problems the country is facing. The years of corruption, civil war, military rule and mismanagement have hindered economic growth of the country. Nigeria is endowed with rich human and natural resources, but those resources have not been effectively utilized in order to yield maximum economic benefits. This is one of the primary causes of unemployment and poverty in Nigeria.

Again, peer group pressures can lead some people into prostitution. Maria (2007) is of the view that, many young women and girls fall prey to pressure from their peers, who they perceive as having made it. The young girls and women want to make it too and be able to flaunt their influence like those people not knowing or caring how they made it.

In addition, some parents have formed the habit of sending their children away for unnecessary reasons due to one thing or the other which is very bad and can lead the child into any business like prostitution. Most parents do not give the children the proper guidance and counselling, they over pamper them, they allow them mingle with the wrong peers; this could lead to deviant act criminal behaviour as well as prostitution (Alobo & Ndifon, 2014). Many sex workers engage themselves in this business just for the

fun of human sexuality and not for economic benefit or frustration (Ewah, 2010).

Finally, laziness is a disease that affects our youth today and can lead to prostitution that is seen as an easy business that generates fast money. Some youth need manner from heaven, in fact, they do not want to suffer to make a living and this is affecting the society, they see prostitution as a free business one can do without employment and stress. Notwithstanding, Otengwo (2002) observed that many ladies turn themselves to prostitution just for the sake of purchasing power and they have unaccountable ways of seducing those they perceived as rich people. This directly implies that most of the ladies today do not believe in the philosophy of hard-work but rather prefer selling themselves instead of working to get what they want.

Prostitutes are vulnerable and are occasionally targeted by serial killers who may see them as easy targets or use the religious and social stigma associated with prostitutes to justify their murder. Because they are criminals in most jurisdictions, prostitutes are less likely than law-abiding citizens to be tracked down by police if they go missing, making them easy prey for predators. More so, the spread of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) such as HIV is linked to prostitution. Massive transmission among sex workers and clients is one of the main reasons for HIV's rapid spread in Nigeria. In

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Africa, prostitution is linked to HIV infection, with one study finding that encounters with prostitutes cause 84% of new HIV infections in adults, as well as other sexually transmitted diseases such as gonorrhoea, pelvic inflammatory diseases, and syphilis (Alobo & Ndifon, 2014). Multiple sex partners and limited safe sex practice increase the risk of HIV infection. Some customers are willing to pay more for a sexual encounter if they don't have to use a condom. According to research conducted by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, the rate of HIV infection for prostitutes who smoke crack cocaine is three times higher (Alobo & Ndifon, 2014). More so, early pregnancy for minors, rape, tuberculosis, post-traumatic stress disorder, assault, and other acts of violence are all linked to prostitution (Alobo & Ndifon, 2014).

When it comes to the economic health issue of prostitution, it is argued that street prostitution is not victimless because it can harm a neighborhood's reputation and quality of life, as well as depreciate property value. According to Maxwell et al (2000), there is a strong link between prostitution, drug use, drug selling, and involvement in non-drug crime, particularly property crime. Because prostitution is illegal in many jurisdictions, its substantial revenue does not contribute to state tax revenues, and its workers are not routinely screened for sexually

transmitted diseases, which can be dangerous in cultures that value unprotected sex and result in significant health-care costs. Prostitution also reduces the value of property and lowers women's status.

Prostitution is often divisive in the society in which it occurs. Its presence may cause moral outrage among religious people, who see it as a threat to the moral codes enshrined in their scriptures. Others, on the other hand, are simply curious or see it as a necessary evil. Many feminist and women's organizations oppose prostitution because they see it as a form of female exploitation and male dominance over women, as well as a practice that is a result of the patriarchal social order that currently exists (Alobo & Ndifon, 2014).

Another challenge of prostitution in the society is what is called 'Post -Traumatic Stress Disorder' (PTSD). Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder is characterized by anxiety, depression, insomnia, irritability, flashbacks, emotional numbing, and hyper-alertness. Symptoms are more severe and long-lasting when the stressor is of human design. PTSD is normative among prostitutes, especially women. Rae a former prostitute shared her story on Dec. 8, 2016, on mumsnet.com titled "I Didn't Think of My Prostitution as Traumatic but It Left Me with PTSD" She opined thus;

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It took me a long time to fully understand my symptoms; the irritability, the anger, the fear, the strange existential sense that life no longer had any purpose... Not all women in prostitution will suffer from PTSD, but many of us do; even in the most conservative findings, prostitutes are shown to be significantly more likely to suffer from PTSD than the general population. For us, it is the site of our suffering and the cause of our enfeeblement. Only by confronting that, have I begun to heal (Rea, 2016).

There could be a serial depression as a result of a change of Identity. Pimps create a rapid emotional dependency for the prostitute by starting or changing the prostitute's name as a means of removing her from her identity and past. Studies have then shown this could lead to bothersome symptoms and depression in the prostitute.

The prostitutes who break away from prostitution may resort to what is called 'Self Hate'. This occurs as a result of the pimp breaking the prostitute's psyche and spirit. Pimps often use psychological power and brainwashing to break the prostitute's psyche and spirit; other means of ownership used by pimps are specific symbolic tattoos. All these acts are internalized by the prostitute, resulting in intense self-hate which may continue years after breaking away from prostitution. It may also result to Low self-esteem, as a result,

pronounced perception of the prostitute as an object who supplies a financial income for the pimp. When a prostitute is perceived as body parts, a commodity for sexual pleasure, their feelings and emotions are irrelevant.

A Deontological Critique of Prostitution

The reasons behind the act of prostitution may seem genuine in the sight of the majority who adored the act. But, adopting Immanuel Kant deontological ethics, one would then ask if prostitution should be universalized when everyone is affected by the same challenges enumerated above. The answer to this question will inadvertently be no. So, Kant will then recommend that if prostitution cannot be legalized to serve a universal purpose, it should never be heard of, not minding its practice. So, on this view point, it is obvious that prostitution is wrongful as it lacks universal acceptability. The universal acceptability here means that it's not everyone that will share a green eye towards prostitution and as such, we ought to do such which when brought to the faces of everyone, they would be acceptable or have a universal acceptance.

In another point of deontology, Kant argued that to act in the morally right way, one must act from duty (Kant, 2008). This begins with an argument that the highest good must be both good in itself, and good without qualification. Something is 'good in itself' when it is intrinsically good, and

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'good without qualification' when the addition of that thing never makes a situation ethically worse. So, prostitution as a moral concept lacks the quality of goodness. It is neither good in itself nor good with qualification. So for Kant, your actions are of moral worth only if it coincides with your duties and duties should be performed for its own sake. Kant believed that ethical actions should be the result of following universal moral laws such as don't lie, don't cheat etc. With this, Kant has maintained that prostitution cannot be accepted because it cannot be accepted as a universal moral law.

In another instances of Kant, prostitution is condemned as a mere means to end and not the end in itself. The second maxim of Kant focuses on how human beings should be treated. In his words, "Act so that you treat humanity, whether in your own person or in that of another, always as an end and never as a mere means" (Kant, 1959). For Kant, we use objects and things as mere means all the time. I might use this pen to write; therefore, pen becomes a mere means to write something. Pen becomes the mere means to achieve the end of writing. Once the ink of your pen is finished you would throw your pen, as no longer it would serve any purpose to you. This is exactly what prostitutes do. They use men/women just for the means of gratifying their financial want and satisfying their financial need.

Putting in a different way, the prostitutes only need you when they want to satisfy their sexual urge. Immediately this need is satisfied, your business with them terminates instantly until when there is another financial/sexual need or business. Kant says it's alright to use things and objects but not human beings. Human beings are 'End-in –themselves'. No human being can be treated as an object for some use. Humans exist for themselves and 'in- themselves'. Kant never said that we don't use each other as means. We all are human beings and we are dependent on each other, we rely on each other. For example, you might use your mother's skill of 'cooking' while having food, as she is cooking food for you. You might use your father's money to pay your tuition fee. You might also use your husband/wife to satisfy your sexual urge. But we shouldn't be using each other as mere means. We are human beings, intelligent and rational enough, we shouldn't see others according to our own benefit. When we treat a human being as a means to achieve an end we end up surpassing her will, autonomy, intellect and reason. If you do this, you are violating the second imperative of Kant. Moral truths are universal and you don't need a God to govern it. So, prostitution uses man for its own gain and because of that, it is out rightly condemned for not following the deontological principle.

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Evaluation and Conclusion

Deontology is the normative ethical theory which states that the morality of an action should be based on whether that action itself is right or wrong under a series of rules, rather than based on the consequences of the action. They are theories that are concerned with what people do, and not about what consequences the action can have. So, prostitution may have “good consequences”, but the act itself is bad.

The consequences of prostitution is greater than its gain despite what the hedonist might present before us. The deontologist has emphasized that prostitution breed greater risk in the society because its presence may cause moral outrage among religious people, who see it as a threat to the moral codes enshrined in their doctrine. The society today is filled with people that have lost the sense of morality and thrive better in impunity. The society is filled with people that cherish sex as a source of living, all their thoughts, minds and attitudes are geared sexual immorality. It is shame that we no longer observe decorum even in the internet that serves as a public gathering of the whites and blacks. So, with this research we believed that anyone that comes across it will have a change of mind and revert from the life of prostitution.

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